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Abstract: Anesthesia is a vital aspect of modern medicine, too often looked upon as a last resort. It plays an important role in the diagnostic and therapeutic procedures carried out today. The success of the procedure varies from survival to mild or severe morbidity and bereavement, and depends to a large extent on the appropriateness with which it is used. This is especially true in pediatric patients, in whom misunderstandings regarding cognitive effects of both anesthesia and surgery in younger children have in the past led professionals and parents to understate its potential benefits. As compared to adults, these potential benefits are greater and the risk acceptance is higher. Failure to relieve anxiety and stress can hinder cooperation and result in procedure termination.

Keywords: acute respiratory failure (ARF), 'anaesthesia', Pediatric Patients.

Relevance: Anesthesia is a vital aspect of modern medicine, too often looked upon as a last resort. It plays an important role in the diagnostic and therapeutic procedures carried out today. The success of the procedure varies from survival to mild or severe morbidity and bereavement, and depends to a large extent on the appropriateness with which it is used. This is especially true in pediatric patients, in whom misunderstandings regarding cognitive effects of both anesthesia and surgery in younger children have in the past led professionals and parents to understate its potential benefits. As compared to adults, these potential benefits are greater and the risk acceptance is higher. Failure to relieve anxiety and stress can hinder cooperation and result in procedure termination. Relief of symptoms in the correct diagnosis, prevention of injury due to uncontrolled, involuntary movements, and provision of a still field for invasive or traumatic procedure are all possible aims. Similarly, therapy

to detract a child from self-destructive behavior and provide pharmacological control of aggressive or other inappropriate behavior can only be successfully accomplished through a variance of anesthesia known as conscious sedation. All are potential beneficial effects of anesthesia, and all warrant its greater use in children. It is the only medical discipline in which physicians/pediatric surgeons have more control on the outcome of a situation and the provision of improved quality of care.

The requirement for anesthesia far outweighs the provision of it. It is not a universally available service and provision is patchy at best. A review in the UK found that services for children are still being delivered in inappropriate adult facilities and by staff who are not specifically trained in pediatrics. As the discipline and distinct specialty of pediatric anesthesia is still relatively young, this is a common problem worldwide, a problem that is often reflected by low quality or inadequate research on the best practice of anesthesia in children. This lack of evidence-based practice can mean the difference between a good and bad outcome and more worryingly, in some cases, it can be harmful (Alkhoury et al.2022).

Importance of Anesthesia in Pediatric Patients

It is not uncommon for patients to associate the word 'anaesthesia' with fear, and more often than not, parents of pediatric patients are no different. Throughout the years, the signs and symptoms of a disease and its treatment have been the focus for patients across the spectrum. The OVID database and PubMed were searched using the keywords 'anaesthesia,' 'children,' and 'parents.' Articles were chosen based on their comparison of child and parent views of anaesthesia, child fears or concerns of anaesthesia, and interventions used to minimize or alleviate child preoperative anxiety. General anaesthesia has proved to be a medical practice unlike any other, and its effects are crucial to the effective recovery and treatment of a disease present in a child. Unfortunately, more often than not, the idea of having to undergo a procedure involving an anesthetic is just as daunting to a child as it is to their parents. Anaesthesia can provoke a significant amount of anxiety in pediatric patients, and the importance of acknowledging and addressing this issue should not be overlooked. Understandably, many healthcare professionals and parents concentrate their efforts on gaining an understanding of the anaesthetic or procedure being performed. However, in doing so the potential long-term benefits and health outcomes of the child can be disregarded. Decision aids, which provide information in a comprehensive and understandable format, can

be a useful tool when gaining child assent for anesthetic procedures, as well as aiding parental informed consent. The chosen anaesthetic should cater to the child's best interests and wellbeing, whilst also taking into consideration the parents' concerns and involvement in the decision-making process.

Unique Considerations in Pediatric Anesthesia

Factors unique to pediatric patients which influence the decisions of the anesthetist are discussed further below. As with all patients, a careful preoperative assessment is required, paying particular attention to any underlying systemic disease. Obviously, the younger and the smaller the child, the more vital is functional capacity of even one organ to the total activity of the entire organ system. This is the major reason for the striking physiological variations between children of different ages and the different responses of young children to illness and stress. Organ function can be assessed through biological tests, but results may not always give a clear answer as to the state of the child's health. A detailed history of any previous illness or hospital admission is thus of great importance. A rapid oral history from the parent may provide practical information for everyday practice. Residence near hospital is of vital importance in emergency situations, and the phone number and transport availability should be checked if parents are leaving the child for an elective admission. Older children may give a useful history in their own right.

Pediatric patients pose unique problems for the anesthetist. The types of surgery and the nature of the underlying disease often differ from that in the adult. For example, congenital heart disease is relatively uncommon in adults, but is a common indication for surgery in children. Similarly, neural tube defects, infantile hypertrophic pyloric stenosis, and the correction of orthopedic deformities are rarely encountered in adult practice. The very wide range of age, size, weight, and state of development from the premature neonate to the adolescent, and the widely differing physiological and psychological responses associated with these developmental stages, further distinguish pediatric from adult anesthesia. Finally, the support of vital functions in neonates and small infants, many of whom present with serious systemic disease, poses a special kind of challenge for the anesthetist.

Challenges in Administering Anesthesia to Children

The information gained in the preoperative assessment leads to preparing the child and their family for the proposed surgery and anaesthetic. With a child who is usually dependent on their parents, the involvement of the parents and explanation to them about what to expect on the day of surgery is very

important. It may be necessary to explain this more than once. Preparation of the child involves an explanation of what will happen on the day of surgery using language that is appropriate to their age and understanding. For simple procedures, this can often be done at the time of surgery. For more complex surgeries or children with fears and anxiety, it may be necessary to explain things in the anaesthetic room or even during a preanaesthetic visit to the hospital.

The preoperative assessment of an adult involves gaining the relevant health and lifestyle information to determine suitability for surgery and the best anaesthetic plan. With children, it is necessary to also gather information regarding their emotional and psychological state. Children's understanding and concepts of healthcare and illnesses change with their age and previous experiences. Therefore, the understanding and compliance of a child towards surgery and anaesthesia can be vastly different from that of their parents. Careful assessment of the child's understanding, fears, and misconceptions will help determine the best way to prepare and proceed with surgery and anaesthetic. Suggestions from parents or carers on how to talk to the child regarding these issues can also be invaluable.

When considering the administration of anaesthetic to children, there are many new and challenging aspects not usually encountered in adult patients. Calne and Williams suggest that when preparing to administer anaesthetic to a child, one must consider three main areas: preoperative assessment, preparing the child for surgery, and the provision of anaesthesia and care throughout surgery.

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